

Synthesis of Δ^2 -cycloPentene-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid : Its Relation to Glutaconic Acid Derivatives.

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It has been shown by Kon and Nanji (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2426) that the ability to exist in stereoisomeric forms is not essential to glutaconic character. Thus the cyclic glutaconic acid derivatives (I) and (II), in which stereoisomerism is precluded due to ring formation, behave like ordinary $\alpha\beta$ -disubstituted glutaconic acids. They form hydroxy anhydrides and their esters yield stable potassio derivatives and can be readily methylated.

Further support has been put forward by a recent paper (Kon and Nandi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1628) by synthesising and studying the properties of the Δ^2 -tetrahydroisophthalic acid (III) and its ester. Though the acid (III) does neither form a neutral nor an enolic anhydride, its ester can readily be alkylated proving the presence of a mobile hydrogen atom.

The present investigation was undertaken to synthesise the Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylic acid (IV) in order to compare its character with that of glutaconic acid derivatives. It may be mentioned here that this acid (IV) is a true $\alpha\gamma$ -disubstituted glutaconic acid in which the two carbon atoms of the propene chain are

part of the five-membered ring. The synthesis has been effected by the following method.

Ethyl butane tetracarboxylate (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65 578) was cyclised in presence of sodium ethoxide, following the method of Uschakov (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 61, 795), and then decomposed with dilute acid giving rise to (VI) with elimination of ethyl carbonate. The ketonic ester was then reduced by means of

hydrogen in presence of platinum oxide and the hydroxy ester dehydrated to ethyl Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylate (VIII). Cold alkaline hydrolysis of this ester gave the unsaturated acid (IV).

A second attempt to synthesise ethyl Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylate by the condensation of ethyl Δ^1 -cyclopentene carboxylate with ethyl oxalate, an observation of Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1265) who studied the condensation of ethyl oxalate with ethyl crotonate and similar esters containing the system $\text{---CH}_2\text{---}\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{---CO---}$, was unsuccessful under various experimental conditions (*vide* Kon and Nandi, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylate formed a stable sodio derivative and could be readily methylated. The methylated ester was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid (IV). The acid appeared to be quite stable to alkali like Δ^2 -tetrahydroisophthalic acid and the acid was recovered unchanged after 7 days' boiling with 20% potassium hydroxide solution. Attempts were made to prepare a neutral or an enolic anhydride without success. This result is not surprising as it can be shown from a model that an acid of this type should not give an anhydride readily.

Thus all the cyclic glutaconic acids (I, II, III & IV), in which stereoisomerism is precluded due to ring formation, display the

properties characteristic to the glutaconic acid derivatives. With the observed facts it can be deduced that, in glutaconic acid derivatives tautomerism and stereoisomerism are independent of each other. Though the isomerides could not be isolated in acids (I) and (II) (the terminal carbon atoms in acids III and IV being symmetrical, the isomerides are identical) still they showed the presence of a mobile hydrogen atom which was responsible for the so-called 'glutaconic character.'

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl cyclopentanone-2:5-dicarboxylate (VI).—A mixture of ethyl malonate (960 g.) and ethylene dichloride (315 g.) was slowly added to a cold solution of sodium (138 g.) in absolute alcohol (1932 c. c.) and the whole was thoroughly mixed by shaking for 10 minutes as a jelly like mass might be formed. The mixture was transferred into pressure bottles (8), securely corked and tied down and heated on a steam-bath for 12 hours. The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed thoroughly with dilute sodium carbonate solution, acid and then water. After removal of ether the brown residual oil was distilled in portions of about 100 c.c. The fraction b. p. 150-192°/8 mm. was redistilled giving 250 g. of pure ethyl butane tetracarboxylate, b.p. 170-190°/5 mm.

The above ester (130 g.) was added to sodium (13 g.) in 260 c.c. of alcohol (dried over calcium) and boiled under reflux for 3 hours. The alcohol and ethyl carbonate were removed under reduced pressure, 200 c.c. of water added and the solution cooled in a freezing mixture and slowly decomposed (below 5°) by addition of 60 c.c. of 20% sulphuric acid. The oil was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and then with water and the ether removed. On distillation some unchanged initial material was obtained together with a lower fraction, b.p. 150-185°/26 mm. which on refractionation gave 30 g. of the ester (VI), b.p. 169-175°/18 mm. It gave intense red colouration with ferric chloride. d_4^{20} , 1.311 ; n_D , 1.4567 ; $[R_L]_D$, 54.86; (calc. 54.55). (Found: C, 57.8 ; H, 7.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 57.9; H, 7.0 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopentanol-2:5-dicarboxylate (VII).—30 G. of the ketonic ester were mixed with 200 c.c. of rectified spirit, 1 c.c. of ferrous chloride solution (0.13 g. per litre) and 2 g. of platinum oxide catalyst ("Organic Synthesis," vol. 8, p. 92) were added to it and shaken with hydrogen. The theoretical volume of hydrogen was absorbed in 8 hours. The catalyst was filtered off, the solvent removed under reduced pressure and the residue distilled at 173-175°/27mm, yield 25 g.

Ethyl Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylate (VIII).—25 G. of the hydroxy ester (VII) in 20 g. of pyridine were cooled in a freezing mixture and 14 g. of thionyl chloride introduced drop by drop with constant shaking. After 12 hours, water was added and the ester extracted with ether. The unsaturated ester had b.p. 168°/21 mm, yield 18 g. $d_4^{24.3}$, 1.1121; n_D , 1.4564; $[R_L]_D$, 54.84; (calc. 53.97). (Found: C, 62.1; H, 7.4. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.2; H, 7.5 per cent).

Ethyl Δ^1 -cyclopentene carboxylate was prepared from cyclopentanone essentially as described by Kon and Nandi (*loc. cit.*) in the preparation of ethyl tetrahydrobenzoate. The dehydration of the cyanhydrin was best effected by means of P_2O_5 in benzene (55%). The use of thionyl chloride alone as dehydrating agent (Ruzicka and Brugger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 399) was found unsuccessful, while pyridine and thionyl chloride gave an yield of 10% of the unsaturated cyanide, b. p. 68°/22 mm. 42 G. of the unsaturated cyanide were refluxed for 12 hours with 170 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 70 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid. The unsaturated ester distilled at 71°/11 mm., yield 30 g.

All attempts to condense ethyl oxalate with ethyl Δ^1 -cyclopentene carboxylate failed when sodium or potassium was used in neutral medium (benzene or toluene) or in alcohol (Kon and Nandi, *loc. cit.*).

Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylic acid (IV).—10 G. of the ester (VIII) were left at room temperature with 4.5 g. of caustic soda in 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of alcohol. After 2 days the alcohol was removed under reduced pressure, the solution diluted, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, evaporated to dryness and extracted with acetone. The acid, m.p. 150.5°, insoluble in ether, was crystallised from hot water in irregular plates. (Found: C, 53.8; H, 5.0. $C_7H_8O_4$ requires C, 53.8; H, 5.1 per cent).

Methylation.—10 G. of the pure unsaturated ester (VIII) were left overnight with 1.1 g. of molecular sodium in 10 c.c. of dry benzene; as only a part of the metal had dissolved, the mixture was boiled on the steam bath for 6 hours. An excess of methyl iodide was then added and the vigorous reaction completed by heating for an hour. The isolated ester could not be distilled without decomposition. It was hydrolysed with caustic potash solution by boiling for an hour. The methylated acid was extracted with ether in a continuous extractor and crystallised from water (charcoal) in fine white crystals, m.p. 225° (decomp.). (Found: C, 56.4; H, 5.7. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 56.4; H, 5.8 per cent).

Action of alkali on acid (IV).—The acid (5 g.) was heated with 50 c.c. of 20% potassium hydroxide solution in a sealed tube at 100° for 18 hours, in another experiment the solution was boiled for a week. The acid was recovered unchanged in both cases.

Unsuccessful attempts were made to prepare the hydroxy anhydride or the anhydride by boiling the acid with acetyl chloride or with acetic anhydride, in both the cases the original acid was recovered unchanged.

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